

Modular programme for Education and Training
EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR

M#2 Principles of Educating Children

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Principles of Educating Children

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Six Core Modules of EduPASS for Early Childhood Educators

The following are the proposed six core modules for Early Childhood Educators education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Early Childhood Educators should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for ECE education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(ECEC\)](#). The ECEC describes the most important the proposal for key principles of a [Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(2014\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing an Early Childhood Educator education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS ECE education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Play	<p>The module teaches the theoretical basis of the concept of holistic development of children, focusing on changes experienced by children aged 3 to 6 years.</p> <p>It emphasizes the importance of physical activity and play in children's overall development and well-being and highlights the benefits of physical activity during childhood, as well as the potential risks of inactivity on overall health.</p> <p>Additionally, recommendations for children's physical activity levels, strategies for implementation, and the development of skills for assessing the recommended daily physical activity level for children are provided.</p> <p>Finally, a theoretical background for developing intervention programs aimed at improving children's daily physical activity levels is presented. It includes practical workshops and the development of skills for designing and implementing programs to enhance children's daily physical activity levels.</p>

2	Principles of Educating Children	<p>This module aims to guarantee the comprehensive development of children through physical education. For this, different learning units, based mainly on the game, will be carried out such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • motor stories • music, dance and movement • energetic games • games with balls • activities that involve balance, development of laterality, coordination and body awareness • manipulative and construction games
3	Inclusive Teaching	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical foundations of the concept of inclusion. This includes the legal background (e.g., UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and national legislation), the requirements and goals of inclusion, and didactic models, principles, methods, and strategies for inclusive teaching. • provide opportunities to practically apply and reflect about the principles, methods, and resources of inclusive teaching using specific teaching/case scenarios.
4	Fundamental Movement Skills, Play and Motor Skill Assessment	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical basics of the concept of fundamental movement skills and play and their importance for children. This includes the structure of fundamental movement skills, their role in children’s development, and didactic principles and methods to promote fundamental movement skills and play. • provide guidance on the practical use of the principles, methods, and resources of teaching/promoting fundamental movement skills and play. • introduce both the theoretical knowledge and the practical skills to objectively measure fundamental movement skills of children using motor tests
5	Hands-on Teaching	<p>This module is designed to enhance the practical skills of Early Childhood Educators through direct participation in learning activities. Through a hands-on approach, participants will develop key skills to foster high-quality interactions with children and create an inclusive learning environment.</p> <p>During the module, Early Childhood Educators will engage in interactive exercises and receive immediate feedback, allowing them to directly apply the pedagogical techniques learned to their educational settings. Strategies for observation and documentation, group dynamics management, and conflict resolution will be addressed, all focused on adapting pedagogical practices to the individual and collective needs of children.</p>

6	Plan, Reflect and Learn	<p>The application of teaching skills, observation and effective decision making is essential to fulfil teaching PAMPS for early childhood and is a cross-cutting capability that should be developed in all ECEs at each stage of their development. The ECE plans, evaluates and reflects each practice and event seeking improvements. In addition, this personal evaluation and reflection underpin a process of ongoing learning and professional development. An important element of this process is the ECE's efforts to with other ECEs in the process.</p> <p>Reflection plays a vital role in early childhood settings. It provides continuous professional development, support, and feedback for all members involved and gives ECEs a safe space to discuss challenging experiences and related feelings. It lays the groundwork for ongoing professional development through consistent self-reflection, community support, and emotional awareness. It's critical that educators can manage the feelings that come with stress to support children's development, communicate effectively with co-workers and families, and find job satisfaction.</p> <p>Questioning what learning and development is taking place to make meaning of what has been observed is crucial for ECE. ECE students should be able to describe why the events are significant to the child and to describe why this experience was important for the child involved.</p>
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Core Module Structure

Core Module	Principles of Educating Children
Module Number	2
Core Module Aim	<p>The aim of the core module is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop basic motor skills in children through playful activities and games to promote coordination, balance, agility and strength.
Module Description	<p>This module aims to guarantee the comprehensive development of children through physical education. For this, different learning units, based mainly on the game, will be carried out such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • motor stories • music, dance and movement • energetic games • games with balls • activities that involve balance, development of laterality, coordination and body awareness • manipulative and construction games
Module Duration	30 hours
Facilities and Equipment	Seminar room and gym (Mainly in the gym)
Methodology	Classes in the gym in which the aim is to put the student in relation with something outside of themselves, to assimilate or internalize different skills or techniques, or in relation with themselves, so that they learn from knowledge, experiences and voluntary and intentional control of their abilities.
Coaching Materials	Logbook / reflection book Didactic materials, manuals and sports materials
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity and health from 3 to 6 years. Spanish Ministry of health • Physical activity and health from 3 to 6 years, Guide for Families. Spanish Ministry of Education and Culture. • Copple, C., & Bredekamp, S. (Eds.). (2009). Developmentally appropriate practice in early childhood programs serving children from birth through age 8 (3rd ed.). National Association for the Education of Young Children. • Gormley, W. T. (2017). The critical advantage: Developing critical thinking skills in school. Harvard Education Press. • Yoshikawa, H., Weiland, C., Brooks-Gunn, J., Burchinal, M. R., Espinosa, L. M., Gormley, W. T., ... & Zaslow, M. J. (2013). Investing in our future: The evidence base on preschool education. Society for Research in Child Development and Foundation for Child Development.
Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Early Childhood Educator Programmes

<p>Module structure (each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 2.1: Basic Motor Skills <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 2.2: Collective Games <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 2.3: Rhythm and Body Expression <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 2.4: Psychomotor and Cognitive Development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 2.5: Ethical and Social Principles in Handling Kids <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours 	
<p>Learning outcomes for Early Childhood Educators</p>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they teach:</p>	
	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamentals of physical education • Teaching methodologies • Safety and prevention • Health 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Didactic skills • Classroom management • Evaluation and feedback • Communication
<p>Learning outcomes for children/learners</p>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to support the children they teach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):</p>	
	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Body parts • Safety rules 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic motor skills • Balance and coordination skills

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthy habits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social skills
	<p>Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enthusiasm • Participation • Responsibility • Autonomy • Empathy • Solidarity • Fair play • Honesty 	<p>Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Cooperation • Inclusion • Diversity • Effort • Improvement
<p>Module Outcomes <i>action oriented outcomes and results for educators</i></p> <p><i>(based on Quality Statements from EU Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care, 2014)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access and Affordability for All: Identify strategies to ensure all children, regardless of socioeconomic status, have access to early childhood education (ECEC) from birth to compulsory school age. • Encouraging Participation and Social Inclusion: Apply collaborative approaches involving local organizations to respect and value the beliefs and cultures of parents. • Professional Development of ECEC Staff: Analyze the impact of initial and ongoing training on pedagogy and children’s outcomes. • Supportive Working Conditions: Evaluate policies affecting group size, child-to-adult ratios, working hours, and wages. • Curriculum Based on Pedagogic Goals: Develop a curriculum addressing cognitive, social, emotional, physical, and language development with common goals and values. • Collaboration and Reflection in Practice: Create environments where staff reflect on practices, analyze effectiveness, and develop new approaches based on evidence. • Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation: Establish systems to collect and analyze information at local, regional, and national levels for continuous improvement. • Governance and Stakeholder Collaboration: Identify the importance of collaboration among governments, stakeholders, and social partners for successful ECEC services. 	
<p>Connection to other Core Module</p>	<p>Module 5: Hands-on-Teaching</p>	

Course Structure

Course Title	Basic Motor Skills		
Course Number	2.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	Provide children with a fundamental understanding of the importance of physical activity and establish a solid foundation for the development of basic motor skills, while promoting positive values and attitudes towards physical exercise and general well-being.		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Development of Basic Motor Skills
	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Coordination Development
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Activities to Record Individually
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to basic motor skills • Running and jumping activities • Throw and catch activities 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hand-eye coordination exercises • Foot-eye coordination exercises • Bilateral coordination exercises 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create and carry out an obstacle circuit • Throws and receptions of different heights • Patterns and movement activities 	

Course Title	Collective Games and Sports		
Course Number	2.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	The main objective is to provide group play experiences that promote physical, social and emotional development in a safe and fun way through playful activities adapted to their age.		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Collaboration and Cooperation Games
	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Team and Strategy Games
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Autonomous Development of Skills and Strategies in Collective Game
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to collaboration • Collaboration activities • Group games 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to team games • Strategy and planning activities • Communication and cooperation games 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating new activities based on what was learned • Record of successful strategies • Reports of reflection and self-assessment 	

Course Title	Rhythm and Body Expression		
Course Number	2.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	Promote the physical, social and cognitive development of children through experiences of rhythm and body expression, providing a safe and stimulating space where they can explore and express their emotions, develop their creativity and improve their motor coordination.		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Exploration of Movement and Rhythm
	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Storytelling through Movement
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Autonomous Body Exploration
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to rhythm • Creative movement • Imitation and symmetry games 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narration with the body • Explorations of themes and characters • Creation of Simple Choreographies 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of own movements based on what was learned • Reflect on what they felt while moving • Create simple choreographies in groups on their own 	

Course Title	Psychomotor and Cognitive Development		
Course Number	2.4		
Course Description / Main Objective	Facilitate an educational environment in which children can develop their psychomotor and cognitive skills in a comprehensive manner, providing learning experiences that promote their physical, cognitive and emotional development		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Sensory and Motor Exploration
	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Cognitive Development through Play
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Sensory and Creative Exploration
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensory stimulation • Development of gross motor skills • Development of fine motor skills 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stimulation of creative thinking • Development of logical thinking • Language and communication development 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of own games based on gross and fine motor skills • Reflect on what they felt executing different skills. • Record themselves doing activities that involve fine and gross motor skills 	

Course Title	Ethical and Social Principles in Handling Kids		
Course Number	2.5		
Course Description / Main Objective	This course is designed for educators to explore ethical and respectful approaches to teaching children. Through lectures, seminars, and self-directed work, participants will learn key ethical principles and practical strategies for fostering a respectful classroom environment. The course also emphasizes emotional development, conflict resolution, and reflection on personal teaching practices, aiming to improve both educator self-awareness and the well-being of students.		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Ethical-Social Fundamentals in Early Childhood Education
	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Strategies for Ethical Application in the Classroom
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Self-Directed Work and Ethical Reflection
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical Theories and Education • Empathy and Equity in the Classroom • Children’s Rights in Education 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conflict Resolution with Empathy • Inclusive Teaching Practices • Ethical Behavior Modeling for Educators 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflective Journaling • Developing a Personal Action Plan • Continuous Self-Evaluation 	